

A STUDY ON THE ADJUSTMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO ORGANIZATION CLIMATE

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Abstract:

The aim of the study was to find out the adjustment among the sample of 600 higher secondary school teachers in relation to organization climate, selected using random sampling technique from Kanchipuram and Thiruvallur districts in Tamil Nadu. The investigator used normative survey method for the study. Teachers Adjustment Inventory: (TAI: by Rashmi Ojha, 1990) and School Organizational Climate Description Questionnaire (Nain Sing and Anupama Katoch-2017) were used for the study. Mean, Standard Deviation. 't' test, ANOVA and Karl Pearson's Product Moment Correlation were used as statistical techniques to analyse the data. The findings of the study revealed that the teachers had moderate level of adjustment and organization climate. No significance difference was found in the adjustment of teachers in terms of gender, teaching experience and district but differed in terms of type of school. Female teachers were better than the male teachers in the organization climate and no significant difference in terms of other variables. It was also found that there was a high relationship between adjustment and organization climate of higher secondary school teachers. It is recommended that the concerned authorities should take necessary steps to raise the level of organization climate and adjustment of teachers, the pillars of strength, guiding force of students and the main contributor to good education in a society.

Key Terms: Adjustment, Organization Climate and Higher Secondary School Teachers

1. Introduction:

Teacher Adjustment means adjustment of teacher with their school environment, teaching staff, non-teaching staff, students, curriculum etc. Teacher's adjustment is also affected by the conduct of the school, which depends upon the availability of adequate facilities and suitable organizational climate. Satisfied and well-adjusted teacher can think about the wellbeing and learning process of the pupils which determine the performance of individual at work place. Organizational climate should be congenial and soothing to help the teachers to work in a more professional manner. The effectiveness and stability of the schools are mostly based on their organizational climate as well as on the satisfaction of the committed teachers. School organizational climate is the major determinant factor of the teacher adjustment. The school organization not only has to pay utmost attention to the physical setting of the school, class and its structure but also the learning process, enabling the children to understand discipline, punctuality and the sense of service, etc. Hence an attempt has been made, in the present study, to find out the adjustment of higher secondary school teachers in relation to organization climate.

2. Need and Significance of the Study:

Teacher's adjustment plays an important role to determine their success and help them in maintaining balance between their needs and circumstances in which they are teaching. The prime condition of satisfactory adjustment is that the teachers have confidence in their own competence and the environment in which they work. Satisfied and well-adjusted teacher can think the wellbeing and learning process of the pupils which determine performance of individual at work place. Hence, it is necessary that teacher should be fully satisfied from all aspects to perform the duties effectively. Maladjusted teacher is a potential cause of the problem of indiscipline and quality of work suffers but also the development of children who are badly hampered, so that it may be stopped from multiplying in size because it causes disturbance not only to the students but to whole society. Adjustment of teachers will be possible with effective and supportive organizational climate. In this context the researcher felt the need of undertaking a study on the adjustment of higher secondary school teachers in relation to organization climate.

3. Statement of Problem:

The teacher of today not only has to focus on academic matters but keep himself / herself updated with the new proceedings in the teaching profession. For a teacher, to be able to maintain all such duties in the teaching profession and is surely an uphill task manageable only with the prowess of a strong mind endowed with great adjustable features. It provides ability to the teacher to be able to maneuver his/her teaching tactics in the classroom as well as go about smoothly in dealing with the other teaching duties in an institution. Any professional individual is recognized by the efficiency of the individual depends upon many factors such as

organizational climate, professional aptitude, attitude, professional skills, social competence, managerial skills and adjustment etc. Hence the study is entitled as “A study on the adjustment of higher secondary school teachers in relation to organization climate.

4. Review of Related Studies:

Yahya Don and et al. (2021) studied on Challenges for using organizational climate tools for measuring teacher job satisfaction using mix-method of a survey and a semi-structured interview for a sample of 220 teachers in 23 primary schools of Alor Janggus, Kedah. The themes emerged from the semi-structure interviews were student relationships, decision-making, school infrastructure, teamwork and educational creativity.

Shivnath Singh (2020) conducted a study to compare the Adjustment of 600 higher secondary school teachers randomly selected from different Level of Organizational Environment in Allahabad. Teacher Adjustment Inventory by S.K. Mangal and School Environment Inventory (SEI) by K.S. Mishra were used. There was a significant difference between Adjustment and Organizational Environment of higher secondary school teachers in terms of low, average and high level. Teachers of Average level Organizational Environment had better Adjustment than Teachers of low level Organizational Environment. Teachers of high level Organizational Environment have better Adjustment than Teachers of average Organizational Environment. Teachers of high level Organizational Environment had better Adjustment than Teachers of low Organizational Environment of Higher secondary Schools.

Mohd. Moshahid (2017) studied on Adjustment among 105 Government and Private Higher secondary School Teachers selected through stratified random sampling technique. Mangal Teacher Adjustment Inventory (MTAI) was used for the data collection and analyzed using Mean, SD and t-test. The study indicated that government teachers were significantly better adjustment than private teachers. There was no significant difference between the adjustment of government male and female higher secondary school teachers but private male and female teachers differed significantly. No significant difference was found between adjustment of government and private female higher secondary school teachers.

5. Objectives:

- To find out the level of adjustment and organization climate of higher secondary school teachers.
- To find out the significant difference between the adjustments of higher secondary school teachers in terms of gender, teaching experience, type of school and district.
- To find out the significant difference between the organization climate of higher secondary school teachers in terms of gender, teaching experience, type of school and district.
- To find out the relationship between the adjustment and organization climate of higher secondary school teachers.

6. Hypotheses”

- Level of adjustment and organization climate among higher secondary school teachers is high.
- There is no significant difference between the adjustment of higher secondary school teachers in terms of gender, teaching experience, type of school and district.
- There is no significant difference between the organization climate of higher secondary school teachers in terms of gender, teaching experience, type of school and district.
- There is no relationship between the adjustment and organization climate of higher secondary school teachers.

7. Method of Study:

To study the adjustment and organization climate of higher secondary school teachers, the investigator used Normative Survey method for the present study.

8. Population and Sample:

The population of the study comprised of all the teachers of higher secondary schools of Kanchipuram and Thiruvallur districts in Tamil Nadu. A sample of 600 higher secondary school teachers was selected by the investigator using random sampling technique.

9. Tools Used for the Study:

- Teachers Adjustment Inventory: (TAI : by Rashmi Ojha, 1990)
- School Organizational Climate Description Questionnaire (Nain Sing and Anupama Katoch-2017)

10. Statistical Techniques Used for the Study”

Mean, Standard Deviation. ‘t’ test, ANOVA and Karl Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation were used as statistical techniques for the analysis of data in the study.

11. Data Analysis and Findings:

Hypothesis 1: Level of adjustment and organization climate among higher secondary school teachers is high

Table 1: Level of Adjustment of Higher secondary School Teachers

Adjustment	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
	600	22.5333	2.5707

The above table shows that the mean score of higher secondary school teachers is found to be 22.5333 and hence it is concluded that the level of Adjustment of higher secondary school teachers is moderate and thus the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 2: Level of Organization climate of higher secondary school teachers

Organization Climate	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Principal's behaviour	600	56.1186	3.5365
Teacher's behaviour	600	71.2169	3.7392
Total	600	127.3375	5.2614

The above table shows that the total mean score of higher secondary school teachers is found to be 127.3375. The mean score of Principal's behaviour is (56.1186) and the mean score of teacher's behaviour is (71.2169). Hence it is concluded that the level of Organization climate of higher secondary school teachers is moderate and thus the hypothesis is rejected.

Figure 1: Level of Adjustment and Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers
 Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the adjustment of higher secondary school teachers in terms of gender, teaching experience, type of school and district.

Adjustment in terms of Gender:

Table 3: Significance of difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to gender

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' value	Level of Significance
Male	152	22.3026	2.5650	1.2829	NS
Female	448	22.6116	2.5680		
NS-Not Significant, df 598, Critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level					

The above table shows that the computed value of 't' 1.2829 is lesser than the critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to gender.

Adjustment in Terms of Teaching Experience:

Table 4: Significance of difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to teaching experience

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between	9.7313	2	4.8656	0.7343	NS
Within	3955.6019	597	6.6257		
NS-Not Significant, df 2,597, Critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level					

The above table shows that the computed value of 't' 0.7343 is lesser than the critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to teaching experience.

Adjustment in Terms of Type of School:

Table 5(a): Significance of difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to type of school

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between	44.3119	2	22.1559	*3.3563	S
Within	3941.02	597	6.6013		
*S-Significant at 0.05 level, df 598, critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level					

The above table shows that the computed 'F' value 3.3563 is greater than the critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to type of school.

Table 5(b): Scheffe test Scores on the adjustment higher secondary School teachers in terms of Type of School

Type of School	N	Subset for Alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Government	205	22.3876	
Self-financing	209	22.4098	
Aided	186		23.8333

The Scheffe test shows that the mean scores of Aided school (23.8333) teachers are better than the Government school (22.4098) teachers and self- financing school (22.3876) teachers on the adjustment in terms of type of School.

Adjustment in Terms of District:

Table 6: Significance of difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to district

District	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Level of Significance
Kanchipuram	300	22.4766	2.8418	0.5400	NS
Thiruvallur	300	22.5900	2.2661		

S-Not Significant, df 598, Critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level

The above table shows that the computed 't' value 0.5400 is lesser than the critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean score of adjustment of higher secondary school teachers with respect to district.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the organization climate of higher secondary school teachers in terms of gender, teaching experience, type of school and district.

Organization Climate in Terms of Gender:

Table 7: Significance of difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to gender

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' Value
Principal's behaviour	Male	252	56.1111	3.3752	0.5752
	Female	348	55.9454	3.6262	
Teacher's behaviour	Male	252	70.8055	3.6825	*2.3975
	Female	348	71.5316	3.6312	

*S- Significant at 0.05 level, NS-Not Significant df 598, Critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level

The above table shows that the computed 't' values 0.5752 is lesser than the critical value and 2.3975 is greater than the critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted in terms of Principal's behaviour and rejected in terms of teacher's behaviour. Hence it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to gender on the dimension of Principals' behaviour but significant difference on the dimension of teacher's behaviour. Mean score (71.5316) of Organization Climate of higher secondary school female teachers is more than the mean score (70.5316) of male teachers on the dimension of teacher's behaviour.

Organization Climate in Terms of Teaching Experience:

Table 8: Significance of difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to teaching experience

Dimensions	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Principal's behaviour	Between	47.7150	2	23.8575	1.9239	NS
	Within	7403.1499	597	12.4005		
Teacher's behaviour	Between	2.5519	2	1.2759	0.0942	NS
	Within	8080.6214	597	13.5353		

NS-Not Significant, df 2,597,critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level

The above table shows that the computed 'F' values (1.9239 and 0.0942) are lesser than the critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to teaching experience on the dimension of Principals' behaviour and teacher's behaviour

Organization Climate in Terms of Type of School:

Table 9: Significance of difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to type of school

Dimensions	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Value	Level of Significance
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Principal's behavior	Between	7450.86	2	2.84968	0.2285	NS
	Within	7445.1	597	12.471		
Teacher's behavior	Between	8083.17	2	12.4926	0.9255	NS
	Within	8058.19	597	13.4978		
NS-Not Significant, df 2,597,critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level						

The above table shows that the computed 'F' values (0.2285 and 0.9255) are lesser than the critical value 2.996 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to type of school on the dimension of Principals' behaviour and teacher's behaviour.

Organization Climate in Terms of District:

Table 10: Significance of difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to district

Dimensions	District	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Level of Significance
Principal's behaviour	Kanchipuram	300	56.0066	3.6101	0.0579	NS
	Thiruvallur	300	56.0233	3.4355		
Teacher's behaviour	Kanchipuram	300	71.3266	3.8815	0.6676	NS
	Thiruvallur	300	71.1266	3.8815		
NS-Not Significant, df 598,critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level						

The above table shows that the computed 't' values 0.0579 and 0.6676 are lesser than the critical value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean score of Organization Climate of higher secondary school teachers with respect to district on the dimension of Principals' behaviour and teacher's behaviour.

Hypothesis 4: There is no relationship between the adjustment and organization climate of higher secondary school teachers.

Table 11: Relationship between the organization climate and adjustment of higher secondary school teachers

Correlation			
		Organization Climate	Adjustment
Organization Climate	Pearson correlation	1	*0.1042
	Sig(2-tailed)		0.002
	N	600	600
Adjustment	Pearson correlation	*0.1042	1
	Sig(2-tailed)	0.002	
	N	600	600
Degree of freedom = 598, Critical value at 0.05 level = 0.079			

The above table shows that the computed value of 'r' 0.1042 is greater than the critical value of 0.079 at 0.05 level of significance and hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a high relationship between the Organization Climate and Adjustment of higher secondary school teachers.

12. Recommendations Based on the Findings of the Study:

- The mean scores of Aided school (23.8333) teachers are better than the Government school (22.4098) teachers and self- financing school (22.3876) teachers on the adjustment in terms of type of school. Hence the concerned department should organize seminars, workshops and conferences at district, state and national level every year to make higher secondary school teachers more aware of improving their level of adjustment with students, colleagues, school community and society.
- The findings of the study indicated that the mean score (71.5316) of Organization Climate of higher secondary school female teachers is more than the mean score (70.5316) of male teachers on the dimension of teacher's behaviour. It is recommended to focus on improving the behavior of male teachers, help them for better performance in teaching learning process by understanding the importance of high standards of their behavior in the organization climate.

13. Conclusions:

The study highlighted the importance of adjustment of teachers and organization climate which train the students to become the responsible future citizens. Based on the findings it is recommended that special programme for improving teacher's adjustment which facilitate organization climate are to be incorporated into the school curriculum.. Hence the teachers and the school administrators should provide organization climate which have a strong impact on the performance of students. The development of a positive school climate depends primarily on the supportive behaviors of school principals/heads and the teachers. Hence counseling service to the teachers, school heads and administrators by adopting innovative strategies is necessary to create

supportive, favorable and positive organization climate in the school to tackle all sorts of problems and gain success on all the school outcomes.

References:

1. Ajaykumar and Veersingh (2015) Adjustment of Higher secondary School Teachers in Relation to Organizational Climate. Indian journal of Applied Research .Volume: 5 | Issue: 9 | September 2015 | ISSN - 2249-555X.
2. Bradford, Stephanie .A (2018). Social Work Ethics and Organizational Culture: A Gap in Social Work Education and Social Work Field Education. Retrieved from Sophia, the St. Catherine University repository website: <https://sophia.stkate.edu/dsw/25>
3. Hanie Sadat Sadeghi1 & Mojgan Niknam (2017) The Relationship between Coping Skills with Social Maturity and Adjustment of Female First Graders in High School: A Case Study in Iran. ISSN 1911-2017 E-ISSN 1911-2025. Published by Canadian Center of Science and Education
4. Mohd. Moshahid (2017.) A Study of Adjustment among Government and Private Higher secondary School Teachers. Educational Quest: An Int. J. of Education and Applied Social Science: Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 157-162, April 2017.DOI: 10.5958/2230-7311.2017.00023.X
5. Mustafa Ozgenel (2020) An Organizational Factor Predicting School Effectiveness: School Climate. International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies, 2020, 7(1), 38-50
6. PinkiBaruah et al. (2016) Adjustment of Higher secondary School Teachers of Dibrugarh District, Assam. International Journal for Research in Education (Vol. 5, Issue: 4, June-July : 2016 (IJRE) ISSN: (P) 2347-5412 ISSN: (O) 2320-091X
7. Shivnath Singh (2020) To Compare the Adjustment of Teachers of Different Level of Organizational Environment of Higher secondary Schools. Shodhshauryam, International Scientific Refereed Research Journal © 2020 SHISRRJ | Volume 3 | Issue 1 | ISSN : 2581- 6306
8. Yahya Don, Mohd Faiz Mohd Yaakob, Wan Rozimi Wan Hanafi, Mat Rahimi Yusof, Muhamad Dzahir Kasa, Mohd Sofian Omar-Fauzee, Hareesol Khun In-Keeree (2021) Challenges for using organizational climate tools for measuring teacher job satisfaction. International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE) Vol. 10, No. 2, June 2021, pp. 465~475 ISSN: 2252-8822, DOI: 10.11591/ijere.v10i2.20703.